

THE OPPORTUNITIES OF BIG DATA APPLICATION IN SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT**Verner D.***master's degree**V.N. Karazin Kharkiv National University***Abstract**

The article examines the opportunities of Big Data application in supply chain management. It analyzes various data analytics methods, including descriptive, predictive, and prescriptive analytics. The impact of these methods on process optimization is studied. Cost reduction strategies enabled by Big Data are explored. The integration of Big Data in supply chain management (SCM) is emphasized for its potential to enhance operational efficiency. The benefits of improved decision-making capabilities are highlighted. The necessity of equipping supply chain professionals with relevant skills is underscored.

Keywords: Big Data, supply chain management, data analytics, process optimization, cost reduction, operational efficiency, decision-making.

Introduction

The integration of Big Data into supply chain management (SCM) processes has unveiled new opportunities for enhancing operational efficiency, expanding decision-making capabilities, and optimizing overall performance. Big Data is characterized by its significant volume, high processing speed, and diversity. It provides a comprehensive view of the supply chain, enabling the analysis of information from multiple sources, including transactional records, sensor data, social media interactions, and market trends.

The purpose of this article is to explore the applications of Big Data in SCM. It examines various analytical methods, their practical applications, and their impact on process optimization and cost reduction. Understanding the capabilities and advantages of Big Data analytics will enable supply chain professionals to better navigate the complexities of modern global markets, ensuring more resilient, efficient, and cost-effective processes.

Main part. Big Data analytics methods in SCM

Big Data analytics in SCM encompasses a range of methodologies designed to harness the vast volumes of data generated across various stages of the supply chain. These methodologies can be broadly categorized into descriptive, predictive, and prescriptive analytics, each serving a distinct purpose in the quest to optimize supply chain processes [3].

Descriptive analytics focuses on summarizing historical data to identify patterns and trends that provide insights into past performance. This approach employs statistical tools and techniques to analyze data from sources such as transactional records, inventory logs, and shipment details. By converting raw data into meaningful summaries, descriptive analytics helps supply chain managers understand what has happened in their operations. This understanding is crucial for identifying inefficiencies, monitoring key performance indicators (KPIs), and making informed decisions based on past events. Techniques such as data visualization and dashboard reporting are commonly used in descriptive analytics to present data in an accessible and interpretable format.

Predictive analytics, on the other hand, utilizes historical data to forecast future events and trends. This method relies heavily on advanced statistical models and machine learning algorithms to predict outcomes

such as demand fluctuations, supplier performance, and potential disruptions. By anticipating future conditions, predictive analytics enables supply chain managers to proactively adjust their strategies and optimize inventory levels. Techniques such as regression analysis, time series analysis, and classification models are frequently employed to develop predictive insights. The integration of external data sources, such as market trends and economic indicators, further enhances the predictive power of these models, allowing for more comprehensive and accurate forecasts.

Prescriptive analytics takes predictive insights a step further by recommending specific actions to achieve desired outcomes. This methodology uses optimization algorithms, simulations, and decision analysis techniques to suggest the best course of action under various scenarios. Prescriptive analytics is instrumental in addressing complex supply chain challenges, such as route optimization, production scheduling, and resource allocation. By considering multiple variables and constraints, this approach helps supply chain managers determine the optimal decisions that can minimize costs, reduce lead times, and improve overall efficiency. Techniques such as linear programming, integer programming, and Monte Carlo simulations are commonly used in prescriptive analytics to explore different decision paths and identify the most effective strategies.

The application of these Big Data analytics methods in SCM has profound implications for process optimization and cost reduction. Descriptive analytics provides a clear understanding of past performance, helping to identify areas for improvement. Predictive analytics offers foresight into future events, enabling proactive adjustments and better preparation for uncertainties [6]. Prescriptive analytics delivers actionable recommendations, ensuring that decisions are data-driven and optimized for the best possible outcomes. These methodologies create a robust framework for enhancing supply chain resilience, efficiency, and profitability.

Cost reduction strategies

The application of Big Data analytics in SCM not only enhances process optimization but also plays a crucial role in reducing operational costs. By leveraging advanced data analysis techniques, companies can

identify cost-saving opportunities across various aspects of the supply chain. These strategies focus on improving efficiency, minimizing waste, and optimizing

resource allocation, ultimately leading to significant financial benefits (table 1).

Table 1.

Cost reduction strategies enabled by Big Data analytics [4, 5]

Cost reduction strategy	Description	Impact on costs	Examples of Big Data applications
Enhanced demand forecasting	Utilizing predictive analytics to accurately forecast demand, aligning production and inventory.	Reduces excess inventory, minimizes stockouts, and decreases holding costs.	Machine learning models analyze historical sales data, market trends, and external factors to predict future demand.
Optimized inventory management	Implementing dynamic inventory optimization based on real-time data and predictive insights.	Lowers holding costs, reduces obsolescence, and improves cash flow.	Real-time tracking and analysis of inventory levels, automated reorder points, and demand-driven stock adjustments.
Supplier performance management	Assessing and optimizing supplier relationships through performance metrics and data analysis.	Reduces procurement costs, improves supplier reliability, and enhances negotiation leverage.	Analyzing supplier delivery records, quality metrics, and contract terms to identify and address performance issues.
Logistics and transportation efficiency	Streamlining logistics operations through real-time tracking and route optimization algorithms.	Decreases transportation costs, reduces fuel consumption, and minimizes transit times.	GPS data, traffic patterns, and weather conditions analyzed to determine the most efficient routes and schedules.
Production scheduling optimization	Using prescriptive analytics to allocate resources and schedule production efficiently.	Reduces downtime, minimizes labor costs, and enhances equipment utilization.	Optimization algorithms schedule production tasks, allocate labor, and manage machinery use to maximize productivity and minimize idle time.
Waste reduction	Identifying and eliminating waste in processes through detailed data analysis and monitoring.	Reduces material costs, lowers disposal expenses, and improves environmental sustainability.	Analyzing production processes to identify inefficiencies and areas for waste reduction, implementing lean manufacturing principles.
Energy consumption optimization	Monitoring and optimizing energy usage across supply chain operations.	Lowers energy costs, reduces carbon footprint, and improves operational efficiency.	Energy usage data analyzed to identify high-consumption areas, implementing energy-saving measures and technologies.

From the author's perspective, the integration of Big Data analytics into SCM is a transformative force that significantly enhances operational efficiency and decision-making capabilities. The application of advanced data analysis techniques allows companies to predict future trends, optimize resource allocation, and streamline operations with unprecedented precision. This proactive approach is crucial in today's dynamic global markets, where adaptability and swift response to changes are key to maintaining a competitive edge. The continuous monitoring and analysis of data enable organizations to uncover hidden patterns and insights, fostering a culture of continuous improvement and innovation based on empirical evidence [1]. The financial benefits of Big Data analytics in SCM are substantial, particularly in the context of cost reduction strategies. Enhanced demand forecasting, optimized inventory management, improved supplier performance, and efficient logistics are key areas where Big Data analytics drive significant cost savings.

Examples of companies using Big Data in supply chain for cost reduction

The integration of Big Data analytics into SCM has been instrumental in transforming the operational efficiency and strategic decision-making capabilities of

leading companies. By harnessing vast amounts of data, these organizations can optimize inventory levels, streamline logistics, improve demand forecasting, and enhance overall supply chain visibility.

In 2023, **Walmart** undertook a comprehensive reengineering of its supply chain to better meet customer needs through a more intelligent and interconnected omnichannel network. This transformation is driven by the extensive use of data, advanced software, and automation technologies. According to Walmart, by the end of the 2026 fiscal year, approximately 65% of stores will be serviced through automation, around 55% of fulfillment center volume will pass through automated facilities, and the average unit cost is expected to improve by approximately 20% [7].

Walmart utilizes data analytics to monitor product sales and inventory levels in real-time, enabling proactive restocking and optimization of supply chain processes. By leveraging data from various sources, Walmart can predict demand more accurately, manage inventory efficiently, and optimize logistics routes. This real-time visibility reduces out-of-stock situations and improves order delivery accuracy, leading to significant cost savings and enhanced customer satisfaction.

Amazon continues to lead in the application of Big Data analytics to optimize its supply chain operations. Amazon employs a sophisticated multi-echelon inventory optimization system that manages inventory levels across multiple fulfillment centers, optimizing for delivery speed and cost. This system integrates real-time data and predictive analytics to dynamically adjust inventory positions and reduce shipping costs.

Amazon leverages generative AI to enhance decision-making processes, automate routine tasks, and improve demand forecasting accuracy. Utilizing AWS services, Amazon unifies supply chain data to gain end-to-end visibility and drive process automation, enabling real-time monitoring and risk mitigation. Amazon's anticipatory shipping model predicts customer orders and

prepositions inventory in nearby warehouses, reducing delivery times and shipping costs. To further enhance their supply chain capabilities, Amazon has introduced DAOS, an open-source system for data access-aware memory management, achieving up to a 12% performance improvement and 91% memory savings. These advancements allow Amazon to streamline operations, reduce costs, and enhance customer satisfaction, maintaining its competitive edge in the market [2].

In quantitative terms, Amazon's operating expenses increased from \$469,822 billion in 2021 to \$501,735 billion in 2022 and further to \$537,933 billion in 2023, reflecting a 7.21% rise from 2022 to 2023. However, this increase is offset by the substantial growth in operating income (fig.1).

Figure 1. Amazon operating income, billion dollars [8]

This significant improvement in profitability highlights the success of Amazon's supply chain enhancements. The advancements in Big Data analytics and other technological improvements played a crucial role in driving operational efficiency, enabling Amazon to achieve higher profits despite the increase in expenses. In 2022, the company's operating income decreased due to heightened investments in logistics, rising labor costs, and inflationary pressures, which affected overall operational expenses. Subsequent strategic efforts in optimizing supply chain processes and leveraging data analytics led to substantial financial benefits, resulting in a notable rebound in operating income in 2023.

FedEx, a global leader in logistics and supply chain solutions, has revolutionized its operations through the strategic application of Big Data analytics. By leveraging advanced algorithms and real-time data from GPS tracking, traffic conditions, weather forecasts, and historical delivery times, FedEx optimizes delivery routes to minimize congestion and disruptions. This optimization reduces fuel consumption and delivery times while enhancing reliability and efficiency. Predictive analytics and IoT sensors enable proactive fleet maintenance, minimizing downtime and maintenance costs.

In 2023, FedEx reported a net income of \$3,972 billion, up from \$3,826 billion in 2022 [9]. The implementation of Big Data analytics has significantly improved FedEx's operational efficiency and cost reduction efforts. Enhanced customer experience is achieved

through precise delivery windows and real-time tracking, boosting customer satisfaction and trust. Route optimization and improved fuel efficiency have also substantially reduced FedEx's carbon footprint, aligning with sustainability goals. By integrating data across its supply chain, FedEx maintains real-time shipment visibility, facilitating better inventory management and quicker disruption responses. These data-driven strategies underscore FedEx's commitment to leveraging Big Data for supply chain process optimization and cost reduction.

Conclusion

The integration of Big Data into SCM presents substantial opportunities for enhancing operational efficiency, improving decision-making quality, and optimizing overall performance. Big Data analytics methods, including descriptive, predictive, and prescriptive analytics, provide deeper insights into supply chain processes and enable informed decision-making. Descriptive analytics helps identify patterns and trends from historical data, essential for monitoring key performance indicators (KPIs) and determining areas for improvement. Predictive analytics offers forecasts of future events, such as demand fluctuations and potential disruptions, allowing for proactive strategy adjustments. Prescriptive analytics, utilizing optimization algorithms and simulation, provides actionable recommendations for achieving desired outcomes. Together, these methods create a resilient, efficient, and cost-effective SCM system capable of navigating the complexities of modern global markets. It is crucial to note

that successful Big Data implementation requires not only technological integration but also the development of relevant skills and competencies among SCM professionals.

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